

Tracer study of School of International Hospitality and Tourism Management graduates, SY 2017-2020

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Abstract

This tracer study, which was participated in by a total of forty-six (46) BS Hospitality and Tourism Management graduates of St. Dominic College of Asia (SDCA) from batches 2017 to 2020, had utilized a descriptive type of research to better illustrate the results based on data. A survey instrument was administered using Survey Monkey. The respondents had confirmed the relevance of the Hospitality and Tourism Management programs of the SDCA to their current profession. The range of courses, teacher-student relationships, and the teaching-learning environment are among the variables they gave much value. On one hand, extracurricular activities and library resources, which are also significant in their profession, were among the least appreciated variables.

Keywords: Tracer study; Hospitality management; Tourism management; Graduates.

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Introduction

Quality education provides the foundation for equity in society. It can be measured in various aspects like the availability of qualified and competent teachers, co-curricular activities, extracurricular activities, school facilities, laboratories, and equipment. For the researcher, however, the most important measurement is the ability of the school to give meaningful life to its graduates in the form of appropriate employment; thus, this tracer study is initiated.

As part of the Hospitality and Tourism Management curriculum, students are required to undertake general education in core subjects that are needed in their professions. Core competencies are the resources and capabilities that comprise the strategic advantages of an individual. According to the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) Memorandum Order no. 62 series of 2017, core courses that can develop specific skills and knowledge that students need to possess in the field of hospitality and tourism include some of the following topics: risk management as applied to safety, security, and sanitation; legal aspects in tourism and hospitality; tour and travel management; fundamentals in foodservice operations (Licuanan, 2017).

Educational institutions in the Philippines offering hospitality and tourism management programs are dedicated to employing their students with a robust understanding and the need for continuous development of the managerial and operational competencies of hospitality and tourism through reflective practice, like hands-on experience consistent with global standards. These institutions confirmed that graduates of the Hospitality and Tourism Management programs are primed as hoteliers, restaurateurs, managers, and tourism professionals.

Hospitality and tourism management graduates have learned relationships to the current research objectives. These objectives play an important function in adding credibility and authenticity to the institutional programs. Furthermore, they highlighted that studying hospitality and tourism gave them the great opportunity to be well-rounded in the industry and face challenges in their chosen field (Stone et al., 2017; Tolkach & Tung, 2019).

Hospitality does not necessarily mean cooking, but it gave the students the opportunity to develop their personality, critical thinking and decision-making skills, and communication skills (Ampountolas et al., 2019; Testa & Sipe, 2012). Graduates, especially in hospitality and tourism management, require a lot of patience, especially in learning new foreign languages and making tour packages (De Guzman et al., 2021; Menes et al., 2019). Professionals need to be updated on the different trends in the tourism and hospitality industry (Davahli et al., 2020; Pencarelli, 2020). Given how important it is that graduates have the abilities that the industry calls for, the measurement depends on the abilities that the graduates acquired while enrolled in the school (Clarke, 2018; Rahmat et al., 2012).

Concerning Mayo and Thomas-Haysbert's (2005) study on the fundamental skills required of graduates in hospitality and tourism management, results showed that the main qualities required are the ability to oversee and motivate subordinates, adapt to financial and revenue management skills, and enhance effective communication skills. The results offer fresh perspectives on the abilities graduates must possess, particularly in the areas of revenue and financial management. The critical aspect of the findings is that the requisite skills associated with the competencies must be infused in all courses and assessed yearly. The study emphasized how important it is to update and revise the curriculum and design of the Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management and Tourism Management programs to better meet the needs of the labor market.

Methodology

A descriptive research design was utilized in this undertaking. The survey questionnaire was administered to the 46 respondents from St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoar, Cavite, Philippines, particularly from the BS Hospitality Management and BS Tourism Management programs, using Survey Monkey. It includes the profile of the respondents, which assessed the following: sex, civil status, year graduated, respondent's designation to their employment, nature of employment, employment status, nature of employment, place of work, monthly income, job connection to college degree, number of years in the current work, current job after college, reasons for staying in the current job, job after graduation, length of time in securing job after graduation, and reasons for not seeking job after graduation. Furthermore, it also determined the contribution of the program of study to personal and professional growth, as well as the assessment of the hospitality and tourism degree programs in this school.

An informed consent was obtained by the researchers, wherein voluntary participation is encouraged in this study. Respondents were assured that all information would be confidential and would only be used for research purposes. Frequency and percentage distribution were utilized to identify the profile of the respondents, while the weighted mean was used to assess the values and attitudes that they acquired from the school regarding the contribution of the program of study to personal and professional growth and their stay in hospitality and tourism degree programs. Tables and charts were also used to see how effective their knowledge and skills are and how they impacted the students.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Respondents' Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	15	34.09%
Female	29	65.91%
Total	44	100.00%

Figure 1. Respondents' Sex

Table 1 determines the respondents' sex. It shows that most of the respondents who took part in the undertaking were female with a percentage score of 65.91 or a frequency of 29 respondents. Male respondents got a percentage of 34.09 or a frequency of fifteen (15). Two (2) respondents skipped answering this part of the research.

Table 2. Respondents' Civil Status

Civil Status	Frequency	Percentage
Single	41	93.18%
Married	3	6.82%
Separated / Annulled	0	0.00%
Widowed	0	0.00%
Total	44	100.00%

Figure 2. Respondents' Civil Status

It is evident in Table 2, which is civil status, that this result was dominated by respondents who are single based on the frequency of 41 or a percentage of 93.18. Three (3) respondents or 6.82% are married. Two (2) respondents skipped answering this part of the research.

Table 3. Hospitality and Tourism Batch

Batch	Frequency	Percentage
2020	11	27.50%
2019	10	25.00%
2018	8	20.00%
2017	11	27.50%
Total	40	100.00%

Figure 3. Hospitality and Tourism Batch

It can be deduced from Table 3, which is the year that respondents graduated, that this result was participated mostly by graduates from batches 2017 and 2020 as they both obtained the highest frequency score of 11 or a percentage of 27.50. The said rank was seconded by the respondents from batch 2019 based on the frequency of 10 or a percentage of 25 and batch 2018 followed with a frequency rating of eight (8) or a percentage of 20. Six (6) respondents skipped answering this part of the research.

Table 4. Respondent’s Designation

Batch	Frequency	Percentage
Executive / CEO	1	3.23%
Managerial	4	12.90%
Supervisory	3	9.68%
Rank and File	11	35.48%
Others	12	38.71%
Total	31	100.00%

Figure 4. Respondent’s Designation

Table 4 shows the respondent’s designation. It can be seen in this table that most of the respondents answered others and have their own position on their respective companies based on the highest frequency of 12 or a percentage of 38.71. Secondly, graduates who are rank and file employees on their respective companies have a frequency of 11 or a percentage of 35.48. Graduates under managerial levels are also closely based on a frequency of four (4) or a percentage of 12.90. Not so far are the graduates under the supervisory level based on the frequency of three (3) or a percentage of 9.68. Interestingly, 3.23% or a frequency of one (1) respondent is now holding an executive position or chief executive officer (CEO).

Fifteen (15) respondents skipped answering this part of the research. This shows that being in this position is also indicative of one’s success in their chosen field, aside from having a good job as soon as they finish their college education (Wong et al., 2017).

Table 5. Nature of Employment

Nature of Employment	Frequency	Percentage
Self-employed	7	21.21%
Private	25	75.76%
Public	0	0.00%
Others	1	3.03%
Total	33	100.00%

Figure 5. Nature of Employment

In Table 5, which is the nature of employment, it shows that the overwhelming number of the respondents were employed by private companies based on the frequency of 25 or a percentage of 75.76, while no respondents opted to be employed in government. Some graduates preferred to manage their own business with seven (7) respondents or a percentage of 21.21. One (1) respondent answered others, although it did not specify what job he or she took. Thirteen (13) respondents did not answer this part.

Table 6. Employment Status

Employment Status	Frequency	Percentage
Probationary	7	21.21%
Contractual	4	12.12%
Casual	3	9.09%
Permanent	15	45.45%
Others	4	12.12%
Total	33	100.00%

Table 6. Employment Status

In Table 6, which is the employment status, most of the respondents were permanently employed in their respective industries based on the highest frequency of 15 or a percentage of 45.45. This result is followed by those with probationary (21.21%), contractual (12.12%), and casual (9.09%). One (1) respondent answered others, although they did not specify their employment status. Thirteen (13) respondents did not answer this part.

Table 7. Respondents’ Place of Work

Place of Work	Frequency	Percentage
Local	28	82.35%
Abroad	6	17.65%
Total	34	100.00%

Figure 7. Respondents’ Place of Work

It can be deduced from Table 7, which is the respondents’ place of work, that twenty-eight (28) or 82.35% of the respondents opted to stay in the Philippines for employment, while only six (6) or 17.65% decided to work abroad. Twelve (12) respondents skipped answering this portion.

Table 8. Respondents’ Monthly Income

Employment Status	Frequency	Percentage
Below 10,000	3	8.82%
10,000-20,000	16	47.06%
20,000-30,000	7	20.59%
30,000-40,000	2	5.88%
40,000-50,000	2	5.88%
50,000-60,000	2	5.88%
60,000 and above	2	5.88%
Total	34	100.00%

Figure 8. Respondents’ Monthly Income

Interestingly, in Table 8, which is the respondents’ monthly income, the data ruled out that most of the graduates have been earning an average amount of Php 10,000 to 20,000 monthly based on the highest frequency of 16 or a percentage of 47.06. Very few respondents (n = 2) or a percentage of 5.88 have been earning the amount of Php 31,000 or higher every month. Twelve (12) respondents did not answer this part. Salary is a factor in understanding how becoming a professional could change the lives of the graduates (Wan et al., 2014).

Table 9. Job Connection to College Degree

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	23	67.65%
No	11	32.35%
Total	34	100.00%

Figure 9. Job Connection to College Degree

One problem that graduates are encountering nowadays is the issue of underemployment. In Table 9, which determines the job connection to college degree, the data proved that this is never an issue to most of the respondents as they attested their current employment relates to their college education based on the highest frequency of 23 or a percentage of 67.65. Eleven (11) respondents or a percentage of 32.35 claimed that their work is not at all related to their college education. Twelve (12) respondents skipped this part.

Table 10. Number of Years in Current Work

Employment Status	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 1 year	13	38.24%
1-3 years	15	44.12%
4-6 years	4	11.76%
7-10 years	0	0.00%
Others	2	5.88%
Total	34	100.00%

Figure 10. Number of Years in Current Work

In Table 10, which is the number of years in current work, the data shows that most of the respondents have been employed by their company for one (1) to three (3) years now based on the highest frequency of 15 or a percentage of 44.12, while some worked for less than one year (38.24%) and four (4) to six (6) years (11.76%). It is also shown that none of the graduates have worked for seven (7) to ten (10) years, while others have cited their respective number of years they have worked. Twelve (12) respondents skipped this part.

Table 11. Current Job as the Respondents’ Job After College

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	23	67.65%
No	11	32.35%
Total	34	100.00%

Figure 11. Current Job as the Respondents’ Job After College

The data revealed in Table 11, which is the current job as the respondents’ job after college, that more respondents’ current jobs are not their jobs after graduation based on the frequency of 19 or a percentage of 55.88. Those who opted to stay in their first job have a percentage of 44.12 or a frequency of 15 respondents. Twelve (12) respondents did not answer this part.

Reasons for Staying in the Current Job

- In line with the college course
- I can work anywhere and anytime I want.
- Challenging, interesting, and fun.
- Good salaries and benefits.
- Enjoying the career I have chosen
- New environment, higher income, related to my bachelor’s degree.
- Good compensation and degree related job
- Work from home / incentives / benefits
- This gives me monetary support for my family, and it enables me to discover more about myself.
- I love my work.
- I want to gain more experience and how to manage the designated work.
- Money
- Because of the good opportunities waiting for me.
- Good benefits
- Because of pandemic, that's why I stayed in retail industry. All the jobs in my field have been closed.
- Due to pandemic
- I am enjoying my work and still learning new things.
- To provide for my family

- Salary, benefits, environment, experience
- Based on my experience, they really give importance to all their employees, especially in the field of food industry. In my training journey, we had meetings, teach and study regarding food industry, and many more. They taught us like we're going back to school because some of my co-workers forgot about what they've studied back then. I really love their way of training employees, as they don't forget the important things about food industry.
- I have a dream
- Enjoyment
- Good experience
- I earn 6 to 7 digits a month
- Career growth
- Steppingstone in other countries
- I am learning a lot from this job, and I know that it will give me benefits soon.
- Higher offer and career change
- Peers

Based on the list above, which identifies the reasons for staying in the current job, most of the respondents opted to stay in the current job because it is aligned to their course. It was also mentioned that they wanted to gain more experience and grab it as an opportunity to learn more in their current job. Some of the respondents mentioned that the salary and benefits they are receiving are the main factors that affect their decision to stay.

As mentioned in the article of Flowers and Hughes (1973) as cited by Davidescu et al. (2020), achievement, acknowledgment, accountability, development, and other factors related to an individual's motivation at work are some of the factors that contribute to job satisfaction among employees. Workplace environmental pressures include issues like policies, amenities, coffee breaks, pay, incentives, and the like. Other elements include familial relationships, financial commitments, community links, outside employment options, and so forth. It discusses why each type of employee stays and illustrates the connection between environmental conditions and job happiness for four different types of employees.

Job After Graduation

- Passenger service agent
- Freelancer
- Customer service associate (CSA)
- Food and Beverage Server
- Guest Service Associate
- Fry cook
- Sales Advisor
- Content Creator/ Insect breeder
- Cashier
- Room Attendant
- Businesswoman
- Barista
- Receptionist at hotel
- Barista Trainer at Rustans Coffee Corporation
- Coffee shop staff
- Crew member at Kenny Rogers
- Kitchen Staff - Assembler
- Line Cook

- Travel Agent
- Logistics
- Barista
- College Professor
- Travel Consultant
- Crewing Assistant

It is evident in the list above, which shows the job after graduation, that majority of the respondents were able to work in the hospitality and tourism industry. The respondents were highly motivated to seek job opportunities that are aligned to their field of specialization after they graduate. It is noticeable that there are no graduates who were able to work on the cruise at once since they must gain work experience on land.

Table 12. Length of Time in Securing Job After Graduation

Length of Time	Frequency	Percentage
Less than a year	20	71.43%
1 year	0	0.00%
2 years	1	3.57%
3 years and above	1	3.57%
Others	6	21.43%
Total	28	100.00%

Figure 12. Length of Time in Securing Job After Graduation

Table 12 shows the length of time in securing job after graduation. It can be shown that most respondents were able to secure jobs after graduation in their respective industries based on the highest frequency of 20 or a percentage of 71.43. Each of the respondents got their jobs for two or even three years, while others took some years to apply for their respective jobs. Eighteen (18) respondents did not answer this part.

Table 13. Reasons for Not Seeking Job After Graduation

Reasons	Frequency	Percentage
Family concern	5	17.86%
Lack of work experience	2	7.14%
To have a longer rest / vacation while working	3	14.29%
Take care of family business	4	10.71%
Others	14	50.00%
Total	28	100.00%

Table 13 identifies the reasons for not seeking job after graduation. The respondents were asked to give their opinions about some hospitality and tourism graduates who would opt not to be employed immediately. Various answers were given by 28 respondents. However, the most notable reason was about other responses with the highest frequency of 14 or 50%, which did not specify at all. Some of them explained family concerns, lack of work experience, having a longer rest or vacation before working, and taking care of family business. Eighteen (18) respondents skipped answering this portion of the undertaking.

Table 14. Contribution of the Program in SDCA to Personal and Professional Growth

Contribution of the Program	Weighted Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
Academic Profession	3.54	Very Good	7
Research Capability	3.68	Very Good	5
Learning Efficiency	3.71	Very Good	4
Communication Skills (Verbal and Written)	3.79	Very Good	2
People Skills	3.82	Very Good	1
Meeting Present and Future Professional Need	3.82	Very Good	1
Exposure to Local Community within Field of Specialization	3.75	Very Good	3
Critical Thinking	3.75	Very Good	3
Salary Improvement and Promotion	3.68	Very Good	5
Opportunities Abroad	3.71	Very Good	4
Personality Development	3.79	Very Good	2
Leadership	3.75	Very Good	3
Creativity and Innovation	3.82	Very Good	1
Technological Advancement	3.64	Very Good	6
Grand Mean Score	3.73	Very Good	

Note: 1.00-1.49 – Poor; 1.50-2.49 – Fair; 2.50-3.49 – Good; 3.50-4.00 – Very Good

Table 14 describes the contribution of the program in St. Dominic College of Asia to personal and professional growth. It is evident that SDCA performed its best to develop the students as well-rounded graduates in their chosen fields having a grand mean score of 3.73. It is also noted that for the following criteria: People skills, meeting present and future professional needs, and creativity and innovation, the respondents acknowledged their great contribution to their personal and professional growth with a weighted mean score of 3.82. According to Lesjak et al. (2015), personal development includes professional development. Personal development adheres to fundamental educational concepts and is an integral part of lifelong learning. Along with practical elements, it shares philosophy, ethical framework, and psychology with education.

Table 15 shows the assessment of the graduates of significant variables illustrating the kind of education they have in St. Dominic College of Asia. It can be deduced from the data that most of the respondents believe that they have a good education in SDCA based on the grand mean score of 3.67. As illustrated in the table, the respondents were generally convinced that the following variables like range of courses, teaching and learning environment, quality of instructions, and teacher-student relationships have great effects on their current profession as evidenced by the highest weighted mean score of 3.79. The interdisciplinary learning seconded with a weighted mean score of 3.75, followed by information literacy with a weighted mean score of 3.71. Note however that the library resources and extracurricular activities which are also significant in their profession was the least appreciated variable based on the least weighted mean score of 3.46.

Table 15. Assessment of the Hospitality and Tourism Degree Program of St. Dominic College of Asia

Assessment of the Program	Weighted Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
Range of Courses	3.79	Very Good	1
Relevance to your Profession	3.57	Very Good	7
Extra-Curricular Activities	3.46	Good	8
Premium Given to Research	3.63	Very Good	6
Interdisciplinary Learning	3.75	Very Good	2
Teaching and Learning Environment	3.79	Very Good	1
Quality of Instructions	3.79	Very Good	1
Teacher-Student Relationships	3.79	Very Good	1
Library Resources	3.46	Good	8
Laboratory Resources	3.64	Very Good	5
Class Size	3.64	Very Good	5
Professors Pedagogical Expertise	3.64	Very Good	5
Professors Knowledge of Subject Matter	3.68	Very Good	4
Information Literacy	3.71	Very Good	3
Grand Mean Score	3.73	Very Good	

Note: 1.00-1.49 – Poor; 1.50-2.49 – Fair; 2.50-3.49 – Good; 3.50-4.00 – Very Good

Conclusion and Recommendations

Personal Profile of the Respondents. Most of the respondents who took part in the undertaking were female and single.

Educational Background. It was participated in mostly by graduates from batch 2017 and 2020, seconded by graduates from batch 2019, and lastly from batch 2018. Most respondents landed on their profession related to their specialization after they graduated. The respondents believe in the importance of willingness to learn, loving their passion, and creating a sense of patience, which are the right attitudes to become a future hospitality and tourism professional. A strong academic foundation is essential, which can be established from first year of schooling up to the time of graduation. Teachers are factors, but the same thing with determination and perseverance.

Employment Profile. Most hospitality and tourism graduates of St. Dominic College of Asia are employed in hotels, restaurants, cruise ships, travel agencies, and academe. While most of the respondents were rank and file employees, not far are the graduates now under supervisory and managerial levels. Most respondents were employed by private companies, while there was also a respondent who opted to be employed in government. Most were permanently employed in their respective industries, while they opted to stay in the Philippines for work rather than going abroad. Most respondents have been earning an average amount of Php 20,000 and higher every month. Underemployment is never an issue for hospitality and tourism graduates. Close to perfect statistics proved that their current employment relates to the education they earned from college; most of the respondents have been employed by their company for one (1) to three (3) years now; more respondents' current jobs are not their jobs after graduation; training and experience, excellent work performance, and career growth were the paramount considerations of the respondents in staying in a job. Many of the respondents were able to find a job in a short period of less than a year. Meanwhile, some graduates opted not to work immediately because they must take care of their family business.

Respondents' Perception of SDCA Education. The graduates have a good outlook on the kind of education they have in St. Dominic College of Asia. The respondents noted the following criteria: people skills, meeting present and future professional needs, and creativity and innovation, which were great contributions to their personal and professional growth. They also found the following variables, like the range of courses, teaching and learning environment, quality of instructions, and teacher-student relationships, have great effects on their current profession. On one hand, library resources and

extracurricular activities, which could be significant in their respective professions, were the least appreciated variables.

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are formulated:

1. Establishing open lines for communication with the graduates is essential to maintaining student and school morale. It is recommended that the school's alumni relations be improved.
2. The school must arrange a testimonial event (such as a dinner or acquaintance) with the successful graduates serving as resource speakers to inform the community about areas that require improvement and to encourage students to keep going and fulfill their aspirations of becoming prosperous hospitality and tourism professionals.
3. Using the school's social media accounts and other marketing materials is effective to highlight graduates' academic achievements in the hospitality and tourism program. This research may be utilized for the same.
4. Hiring highly competent full-time faculty members and practitioners for the hospitality and tourism students could be influential to the students' performance and perseverance. They are essential to establishing a good academic foundation for the students.
5. Strengthening the school's culture is important in terms of utilizing different library resources for the hospitality and tourism students.
6. Extracurricular activities should also be emphasized in honing the students' personal and professional aspects to become well-rounded hospitality and tourism professionals.

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